

Dual-objective CO₂ utilization using construction waste toward carbon neutrality and resource circularity (PostDoc No. 1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/294)

Version 3

Description

This Data Management Plan (DMP) is developed within the project No. 1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/294 "Dual-objective CO₂ utilization using construction waste toward carbon neutrality and resource circularity". supported by Activity 1.1.1.9 "Post-doctoral Research" of the Specific Objective 1.1.1 "Strengthening research and innovative capacities and introduction of advanced technologies in the common R&D system" of the European Union's Cohesion Policy Programme for 2021-2027.

The research project utilizes CO₂ to improve the properties of recycled aggregates and fines (RA and RF) from construction and demolition (C&D) waste, with the dual aim of enhancing concrete performance and support carbon neutrality. The project is structured into four work packages. WP1 involves regular monitoring of RA/RF from recycling plants to assess material consistency and recycling feasibility. WP2 focuses on CO₂ mineralization and evaluating the CO₂ uptake of RA/RF. Carbonated RA/RF will be tested as partial replacements for aggregates and cement in concrete, assessing strength, durability, cost, and environmental impact. WP3 investigates whether concrete with carbonated RA can be recycled again (re-recycling). WP4 focuses on dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities.

The purpose of the DMP is to establish a systematic framework for managing the research data expected to be generated during the project's activities. This includes various data types such as experimental photographs, physical and chemical measurement data, and analytical results. In particular, this DMP is to support Open Science by ensuring research transparency and to align all generated data with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable).

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

Dual-objective CO2 utilization using construction waste toward carbon neutrality and resource circularity (No. 1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/294)

Researchers

Jeonghyun Kim (0000-0003-2571-5152)

Organizations

Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Dual-objective CO₂ utilization using construction waste toward carbon neutrality and resource circularity \(PostDoc No. 1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/294\)](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grants: Dual-objective CO₂ utilization using construction waste toward carbon neutrality and resource circularity (No. 1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/294)

Project:

3. License

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Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2026-03-03

4. Templates

Descriptions

DO-CIRC

Experimental outputs will include image files (e.g., JPG, TIFF, PNG) and raw data from material analysis tools such as XRD, TGA, and scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The data, consisting of digital raw files from analytical instruments and photographic documentation of material samples, is expected to be generated through laboratory experiments to quantify the effect of CO₂-treated recycled materials on the performance of concrete.

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1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF
- CSV
- TIFF
- PNG
- JPG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

30

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Existing datasets were considered, but the local characteristics of the C&D waste and the specific CO₂ mineralization parameters of this project require the generation of new, primary data.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data will be useful for researchers in civil engineering and carbon capture, construction and recycling industries, and policy makers developing environmental standards for recycled materials.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

An embargo period will be applied to the dataset until the research results are accepted and published in peer-reviewed journals.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

ResearchGate Data

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

It is expected that most data can be accessed using common software such as Microsoft Office or Google Sheets. Photographic documentation is stored in standard image formats like JPEG or PNG, which can be viewed with any default image viewer. Raw data from specific analytical instruments such as XRD or SEM will be exported into accessible formats like PDF to ensure they can be read without specialized proprietary software.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2029-06-30

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2038-12-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Jeonghyun Kim (0000-0003-2571-5152)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

There are no additional financial costs expected for making the data FAIR after the project realization. The data will be deposited in the ResearchGate Data repository, which provides free-of-charge long-term storage and persistent identifiers (DOIs).

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

Data security will be ensured through physical access control to laboratory facilities, password protection on all institutional computers, and the use of firewalls to protect the network from unauthorized access.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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